

Knowledge of National Medical Commission Guidelines among Faculty Members of Various Medical Colleges in IndiaGupta K.¹, Upadhyai N.², Mittal A.³, Spandana B. S.⁴¹Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Graphic Era Institute of Medical Science, 16th Milestone, Dhoolkot, Dehradun, 248008, Uttarakhand, India²Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Graphic Era Institute of Medical Science, 16th Milestone, Dhoolkot, Dehradun, 248008, Uttarakhand, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Graphic Era Institute of Medical Science 16th Milestone, Dhoolkot, Dehradun, 248008, Uttarakhand, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Graphic Era Institute of Medical Sciences, 16th Milestone, Dhoolkot, Dehradun, 248008, Uttarakhand, India

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Abstract**Objective:** National Medical Commission (NMC) has introduced several guidelines to ensure quality medical education. To implement the guidelines the faculties should be aware of the same and should take active part in rollout of these guidelines. The current study was undertaken to evaluate the knowledge of medical faculties in India about the guidelines by NMC.**Material and Methods:** This cross sectional study was conducted among faculties and Senior Residents (SR's) of various medical colleges in India, using a predesigned pretested self-administered structured questionnaire (Google form) as a data collection tool for data collection.**Results:** A total of 120 responses were obtained from Professors (36.66%) followed by Associate Professors (33.34%), Assistant Professors (24.16%) and Senior Residents (5.84%) in our study. Maximum faculty were from Government medical colleges (50.84%) followed by Autonomous (28.33%) and Private (20.8%). Nearly half of faculty (50.84%) showed excellent knowledge regarding NMC guidelines but (12.5%) faculty showed poor knowledge.**Conclusion:** There is need to conduct periodic faculty awareness program to uplift the medical education.**Keywords:** National Medical Commission, Faculty, Medical education.

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Introduction

The National Medical Commission (NMC) was established to regulate medical education and practice in India in 2019 [1]. The NMC has introduced several guidelines and regulations aimed at enhancing the quality of medical education, transparency, ensuring faculty commitment, and improving patient care [2,3]. One of the key areas of focus is the knowledge and adherence of medical college faculty to NMC guidelines.

Faculty members play a crucial role in shaping the future of medical education and patient care. Their understanding and implementation of NMC guidelines is essential for maintaining high standards and ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements. The NMC guidelines are crucial for faculty members, who play a vital role in shaping the educational landscape and ensuring that

students are well-prepared for their medical careers. There is a dearth of research on the level of awareness and knowledge of NMC guidelines among medical college faculty in India. This study aims to throw light on the importance of awareness of faculty members of medical colleges regarding NMC guidelines, which will provide valuable insights to identify areas for improvement in faculty training and development programs.

The number of Medical Colleges in India has increased by 24% in past 3 years and currently 706 medical colleges are running in India with 109,170 MBBS seats [4,5]. Quality medical education is the need of the hour to ensure that the Indian Medical Graduate (IMG) can comply with the standards globally. The NMC Act, 2019, empowers the NMC to prescribe the minimum requirements for annual MBBS admissions, including the accommodation

in the college and its associated teaching hospitals, staff (teaching and technical) and equipment in the college departments and hospitals [1]. The NMC has issued several regulations and guidelines to ensure the quality of medical education, such as the "Minimum Standard Requirements (MSR) for Annual undergraduate medical Admissions Regulations, 2023" [2]. In order to bring transparency, accountability and upgrading the standards of medical education, NMC has implemented stricter guidelines for medical college faculty, including requirements for biometric attendance, close-circuit TV systems and college websites [2].

The current study aims to build upon the existing literature by focusing on the knowledge of NMC guidelines among Medical College faculty across India.

Material and Methods

This cross sectional study was conducted among faculty and Senior Residents (SRs) of various Medical Colleges in India after taking approval from Institutional Review Board (No. GEIMS/IRB/RP 28/2025) dated 14 February 2025. The study was carried out using a predesigned, pretested structured questionnaire which was converted to Google form as a data collection tool for data collection.

The first section of the form contained the consent along with additional information regarding the investigators and the institute involved. The second

section consisted of total 15 close ended questions with four options, of which 5 questions were related to promotion criteria, another 5 related to Minimum Standard Requirement (MSR) 2023 criteria and last 5 questions related to general guidelines given by NMC. Each correct answer was given 01 mark and no negative marking for incorrect answer. An arbitrary score of 5 was graded as excellent, score of 4 very good, score of 3 was good, score of 2 was average, 1 as fair and zero score was graded as poor. All questions were required to be answered before submission. No change in response was allowed post submission. During analysis, personal identifiers were excluded to make survey anonymous. The link of google form was sent to the study participants using social media platform (WhatsApp). The response was automatically captured. A total of 260 responses were received which formed our sample size for the present study. The data collected was analysed using MS Excel. Percentages were calculated for all variables. The data was presented in numbers and percentages in the form of tables. Association between two categorical data was done by using chi square test at p value < 0.05.

Results

A total of 260 faculty and SR's responded through Google form in English language. Among the study participants, majority 40% of the faculty were Professors followed by Assistant Professors (37.3%), Associate Professors (17.6%) and SR's (5%). (Table-1)

Table 1: Designation wise distribution of Faculty

Faculty	Gender		Total n (%)
	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	
Professor	35 (33.6)	69 (66.4)	104 (40)
Associate Professor	16 (34.7)	30 (65.2)	46 (17.6)
Assistant Professor	32 (32.9)	65 (67.0)	97 (37.3)
Senior Resident	7(53.8)	6 (46.1)	13 (5.0)

In our study, maximum faculty members were from Private Medical Colleges (58.1%) followed by Government (33.4%) and Autonomous Medical Colleges (8.5%). (Table - 2)

Table 2: Designation wise distribution of Faculty according to type of institute

Faculty	Government n (%)	Autonomous n (%)	Private n (%)
Professor	32 (30.8)	8 (7.7)	64 (61.5)
Associate Professor	17 (36.9)	5 (52.1)	24 (10.8)
Assistant Professor	34 (35.0)	7 (57.7)	56 (7.2)
Senior Resident	4 (30.7)	2 (53.8)	7(15.3)
Total	87 (33.4)	22 (8.5)	151 (58.1)

In the current study, amongst Professors, majority of them (33.6%) had very good knowledge regarding the promotion criteria followed by (28.8%) having excellent knowledge. Although (26%) Associate Professors had good knowledge followed by (21.7%) having excellent knowledge. It was seen that (34%) Assistant Professors had very good knowledge. SR's (30.7%) had average knowledge regarding promotion criteria. (Table -3)

Table 3: Designation wise knowledge of faculty regarding promotion

Faculty	Excellent n (%)	Very Good n (%)	Good n (%)	Average n (%)	Fair n (%)	Poor n (%)
Professor	30 (28.8)	35(33.6)	18(17.3)	12(11.5)	6(5.7)	3(2.8)
Associate Professor	10(21.7)	7(15.2)	12(26.0)	9(19.5)	6(13.0)	2(4.3)
Assistant Professor	22(22.6)	33(34.0)	21(21.6)	14(14.4)	2(2.0)	5(5.1)
Senior Resident	1(7.6)	3(23.0)	2(15.3)	4(30.7)	1(7.6)	2(15.3)

Statistical Interpretation: $\chi^2 = 22.86$, $p = 0.087$, degree of freedom = 15

Amongst Professors, majority (43.2%) of them had excellent knowledge regarding the MSR 2023, whereas Associate Professors (39.1%) had good knowledge. Only (30.9%) Assistant Professors had fair knowledge. It was seen that Senior Residents

had average knowledge (46.1%) regarding MSR 2023 criteria. The association between designation of faculty and knowledge regarding MSR is statistically significant at 95% confidence interval. (Table 4)

Table 4: Designation wise knowledge of faculty regarding MSR 2023

Faculty	Excellent n (%)	Very Good n (%)	Good n (%)	Average n (%)	Fair n (%)	Poor n (%)
Professor	45 (43.2)	32(30.7)	15(14.4)	6(5.7)	4(3.8)	2 (1.9)
Associate Professor	9(19.5)	13(28.2)	18(39.1)	2(4.3)	3(6.5)	1(2.1)
Assistant Professor	14(14.4)	10(10.3)	15(15.4)	21(21.6)	30(30.9)	7(7.2)
Senior Resident	1(7.6)	2(15.3)	1(7.6)	6(46.1)	1(7.6)	2(15.3)

Statistical Interpretation: $\chi^2 = 100$, $p = 0.00$, degree of freedom = 15

Amongst faculty, Professors (64.4%), Associate Professors (45.6%), Assistant Professors (48.4%) and SRs (46.1%) had excellent knowledge regarding basic NMC guidelines. Poor knowledge was seen in (1.9%) Professors, (4.3%) Associate Professors, (4.1%) Assistant Professors and (7.6%) in SRs. (Table 5)

Table 5: Designation wise knowledge of faculty regarding basic NMC guidelines

Faculty	Excellent n (%)	Very Good n (%)	Good n (%)	Average n (%)	Fair n (%)	Poor n (%)
Professor	67(64.4)	18(17.3)	4(3.8)	8(7.6)	5(4.8)	2(1.9)
Associate Professor	21(45.6)	14(30.4)	4(8.6)	4(8.6)	1(2.1)	2(4.3)
Assistant Professor	47(48.4)	31(31.9)	7(7.2)	5(5.1)	3(3.0)	4(4.1)
Senior Resident	6(46.1)	1(7.6)	2(15.3)	1(7.6)	2(15.3)	1(7.6)

Statistical Interpretation: $\chi^2 = 20.02$, $p = 0.17$, degree of freedom = 15

Discussion:

After extensive review of literature in all renowned databases, no similar researches were found which assess the knowledge of faculties of Medical Colleges about NMC guidelines. In this current study a total of 260 faculty and SR's responded through Google form of which majority (40%) of the faculty were Professors and maximum faculty members were from Private Medical Colleges (58.1%) followed by Government (33.4%) and Autonomous Medical Colleges (8.5%).

Regarding faculty promotion criteria, NMC increased minimum publication requirements for promotion to professorship, 04 publications required for Professorship with at least 2 during Associate Professorship tenure and 02 publications in Assistant Professor Tenure. However, order of authorship is not specified in the latest gazette 2022 for promotion, encouraging collaboration [6,7]. The recommended indexing databases include Medline, PubMed Central, Science Citation Index, Expanded

Embase, Scopus and Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ). Basic Course in Biomedical Research (BCBR) and Medical Education Technology (MET) are required for promotion from Assistant Professor to Associate Professor. These guidelines could be beneficial for ensuring compliance and promoting quality research publications in India [8]. Recognition is given to teachers with 8 years of experience in broad speciality or 5 years in super speciality as postgraduate teachers. Importance was given to systematic reviews, meta-analyses and case series in addition to original articles for promotions. There is also removal of criteria for nationality of journal where article is published. Recognition of e-journal publications and inclusion of DOAJ is given as acceptable database [7,9]. With regard to knowledge about promotion criteria in our current study, amongst Professors, majority of them (33.6%) had very good knowledge followed by (28.8%) having excellent knowledge. This may be due to the reason that after becoming Professor

they have completed all the requirements which have been set by NMC and there is no requirement of fulfilling any promotion beyond Professor Level. Only teaching experience as Professor is required to become Dean in a medical college by NMC. It was seen that (34%) Assistant Professors had very good knowledge as they are in the process of promotion to higher posts and therefore very much aware about it because during those 4 years they have to fulfil the criteria to be eligible for promotion. Majority of SR's (30.7%) had average knowledge which can be explained by the fact that SR tenure is time bound and for promotion to Assistant Professor, publication requirement is not mandatory.

Amongst Professors, majority (43.2%) of them had excellent knowledge regarding MSR 2023, whereas Associate Professors (39.1%) had good knowledge. Knowledge regarding MSR 2023 was more from Associate Professor onwards which may be due to their rich experience in administrative skills, professional networking and their involvement in Faculty Development Programme (FDP), conferences, workshops which helps them to be updated about the latest guidelines. It may be also because Professors and Associate Professors usually hold higher position in various committees and association. It is very likely that senior faculty members will be having more knowledge and awareness than junior faculty.

Faculty members must maintain a minimum attendance of 75% of working days during the academic year. This requirement applies to all teaching faculty involved in medical education [10,11,12]. Faculty are required to be full-time employees of the medical college. They are prohibited from engaging in private practice during college hours to ensure their availability for teaching and administrative duties. The introduction of this attendance requirement aims to address issues such as "ghost faculty," where faculty members may not be present but still receive compensation. By enforcing this rule, the NMC seeks to enhance accountability and improve the quality of medical education. These measures reflect the NMC's commitment to improving the standards of medical education in India by ensuring that faculty members are present and actively participate in the educational process and other academic responsibilities. In this regard, amongst faculty, (64.4%) Professors Associate Professors (45.6%), Assistant Professors (48.4%) and SRs (46.1%) had excellent knowledge regarding basic NMC guidelines which may be due to frequent checks and monitoring by NMC to maintain a minimum level of percentage of attendance throughout the year. Similarly, Rajmohan V Seetharaman's research underscores the variability in knowledge levels among faculty members across

different institutions. This inconsistency points to the necessity for a more uniform approach to guideline implementation across medical schools in India [13]. Study by Habibi also reiterates the importance of training to improve the knowledge of faculty and overall development [14]. Gaber B, conducted a study to evaluate the effectiveness of a faculty development program. The results indicated that faculty who underwent the training demonstrated improved knowledge. This study reinforces the idea that targeted faculty development initiatives can lead to significant enhancements in teaching methodologies [15].

Conclusion

The study highlights the critical importance of faculty awareness of NMC guidelines and the role of FDP in enhancing the quality of medical education in India. While there is a growing recognition of the need for such initiatives, significant gaps in knowledge and implementation persist. Addressing these challenges through targeted FDP and institutional support will be essential for ensuring compliance with NMC guidelines and ultimately improving the educational outcomes for medical students. It is essential for Medical Colleges to develop comprehensive FDP that are aligned with NMC guidelines. These programs should include regular training sessions, mentorship opportunities and resources to support faculty in their teaching roles. Additionally, fostering a culture of collaboration and continuous improvement within medical schools can encourage faculty to actively engage in their professional development.

Limitations: As there are almost no similar studies, there is lack of any standardized measurement methods or process and thus makes it difficult for generalization.

Recommendations

As the NMC guidelines continue to adapt to the ever changing landscape of medical research, it is imperative for researchers and academic institutions to stay informed and adaptable. The introduction of mandatory requirements from time to time by NMC for faculty need to be apprised at institutional level. This can be incorporated by Medical Education Unit (MEU) in the form of monthly Continued Medical Education (CME) or as a part of FDP. This will definitely keep young faculty and SRs abreast with the recent updates. Moreover findings of this study can be used as a baseline data to explore more about the awareness of faculty about NMC guidelines.

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References

1. <https://www.nmc.org.in/MCIRest/open/getDocument?path=%2FDocuments%2FPublic%2FPortal%2FLatestNews%2FPublic+notice+ug.pdf>
2. <https://www.nmc.org.in/rules-regulations/national-medical-commission-minimum-standard-requirements-for-establishment-of-new-medical-college-increase-of-seats-in-mbbs-course-guidelines-2023-reg/> accessed on 6 July
3. <https://bwhealthcareworld.com/article/national-medical-commission-implements-strict-guidelines-for-medical-college-faculty-508343>
4. List of colleges teaching MBBS. National Medical Commission, India. [Last accessed on 2024 Jul 30]. Available from <https://www.nmc.org.in/information-desk/for-students-to-study-in-india/list-of-college-teaching-mbbs/>
5. Mondal H, Soni S, Juyal A, Behera JK, Mondal S. Current distribution of medical colleges in India and its potential predictors: A public domain data audit. *J Family Med Prim Care*. 2023 Jun; 12(6):1072-1077. doi: 10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc 1558 22. Epub 2023 Jun 30. PMID: 37636164; PMCID: PMC10451585.
6. Teachers Eligibility Qualifications in Medical Institutions Regulations, 2022. Notice: CG-DL-E-23022022-233681. National Medical Commission. [Last accessed on 2024 July 31]. Available from: <https://www.nmc.org.in/ActivitiWebClient/open/getDocument?path=/Documents/Public/Portal/NmcGazette/TEACHERS%20ELIGIBILITY%20QUALIFICATIONS.pdf>.
7. Mondal H, Mondal S, Behera JK. Roller coaster of publication criteria: What is new in teachers' eligibility qualifications in medical institutions regulations, 2022? *Indian J Ophthalmol*. 2022 May; 70(5):1845-1846. doi: 10.4103/ijo.IJO_537_22. PMID: 35502093; PMCID: PMC9332971.
8. Ish, Somya; Ish, Pranav¹, Research and publication in India - Beyond ABCDE. *Indian Journal of Ophthalmology* 70(2): p 684, February 2022. | DOI: 10.4103/ijo.IJO_2562_21.
9. Gupta N, Ish P, Iyengar KP, Sakthivel P. New essential criteria for medical faculty in India: A paradigm shift. *Natl Med J India*. 2021 Sep-Oct; 34(5):317-318. doi: 10.25259/NMJI_292_21. PMID: 35593242.
10. [https://www.nmc.org.in/MCIRest/open/getDocument?path=/Documents/Public/Portal/LatestNews/document%20\(76\).pdf](https://www.nmc.org.in/MCIRest/open/getDocument?path=/Documents/Public/Portal/LatestNews/document%20(76).pdf)
11. <https://economictimes.com/industry/education/medical-education-regulator-makes-75-percent-attendance-mandatory-for-faculty-at-medical-colleges/articleshow/107261209.cms>
12. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/education/news/nmc-makes-75-attendance-mandatory-for-faculty-at-medical-colleges/articleshow/107266772.cms>
13. Rajmohan, V, Seetharaman. (2023). Revamping Medical Education in India: New Guidelines for Eligibility Qualifications of Medical Faculty. *Cureus*, doi: 10.7759/cureus.38925
14. Hengameh, Habibi, Shoaleh, Bigdeli, Hakimeh, Hazrati. Effective Teaching in a Medical Education Ph.D. Program: A Qualitative Study on the Perception of Faculty Members. *Acta medica Iranica*, (2023). doi: 10.18502/acta.v61i1.12121
15. Gabr, B. Evaluation of Transfer of Training among Medical Educators after Attending a Faculty Development Program about Competency Based Education. *Journal of Health Professions Education and Innovation*, 2024; 1(2): 47-57. doi: 10.21608/jhpei.2024.260005.1016